

Supplementary Information: Simulation Driven Circularity Assessment of Recycled Paperboard Manufacturing

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S.1. Aspen Plus Model Representation

S.1.1 Raw materials and pulping

Figure S.1 presents the Aspen Plus [1] representation of the pulping stage. Green streams correspond to the layer-specific raw material inputs, while blue streams represent internally recirculated process water distributed to the pulping lines. Freshwater streams are indicated using a distinct light blue colour, allowing differentiation between make-up water and recirculated water. The addition of NaOH is shown in purple, while black streams correspond to the resulting fibre–water slurry mixtures leaving the pulping units. The values denoted as Q correspond to the energy duty of the unit operations and are expressed in kW. In the water reuse scenario, the treated effluent returning from wastewater treatment is introduced into the system at the PW-HEADER mixing point on the left-hand side of the flowsheet, where it is combined with process water prior to distribution to the pulping lines.

Figure S.1. Aspen Plus flowsheet of the pulping stage, showing the distribution of process water, freshwater addition, and mixing with layer-specific raw material streams.

S.1.2 Screening, reject handling and refining

Figure S.2 illustrates the Aspen Plus representation of the screening, reject handling, and refining stages. Black streams entering the separation units correspond to fibre-containing slurry flows, while yellow streams represent the accept streams that continue toward further processing. Brown streams indicate reject flows containing separated contaminants, which are directed through dewatering and reject handling operations. Blue streams correspond to water-rich flows generated during these stages, showing the transfer of water toward the wastewater treatment system, as well as the

returning process water from the board machine. The refining units (REF-OS and REF-SS) are located downstream of the accept streams, with their corresponding duties showed beneath them.

Figure S.2. Aspen Plus flowsheet of the screening, reject handling, and refining stages, showing the separation of accept and reject streams, dewatering operations, and associated water flows.

S.1.3 Forming, pressing and process water

Figure S.3 refers to the model's representation of the forming and pressing stages together with the associated process water system. Black streams correspond to the fibre-rich sheet progressing through the wet end and press sections, while blue streams represent water-rich flows, including whitewater and press filtrate. The collected water streams are directed to the whitewater chest, from which they are redistributed to different parts of the process, including dilution, pulping, and discharge toward the wastewater treatment system. Red streams represent the steam supplied to the heat exchanger

for thermal conditioning, as well as the vapor fraction of the condensate generated during heat exchange.

Figure S.3. Aspen Plus flowsheet of the forming and pressing stages, highlighting the generation, collection, and redistribution of process water within the system.

S.1.4 Drying and steam system

Figure S.4 presents the Aspen Plus representation of the drying stage together with the associated steam generation system. Black streams correspond to the fibre-rich sheet undergoing drying. Freshwater streams are presented with a light blue colour, while darker blue streams represent here the recirculated condensate within the steam loop. Red streams indicate the steam phase, including steam generated from the boiler and supplied to the dryer, as well as the vapor fraction produced during condensate flashing. The upper section of the figure illustrates the steam loop, including freshwater input, pressurization, steam generation, condensation, and condensate recirculation. Grey

streams are used to represent purge flows from the condensate loop and the evaporated water removed during the drying process.

Figure S.4. Aspen Plus flowsheet of the drying stage and associated steam generation system, illustrating the energy supply and condensate recirculation loop.

S.1.5 Coating and final treatment

As shown in Figure S.5, the coating and final treatment stage begins with the addition of a coating stream to the dried board, followed by thermal treatment and phase separation. Black streams represent the solid board progressing through the process, while the purple stream indicates the coating mixture applied to the surface. The subsequent unit operations remove moisture from the coated layer, with the generated vapor stream shown with grey colour, separated from the product. Downstream of this step, the final cooling operation is illustrated, where the product temperature is reduced prior to discharge as the finished board, which is presented by a light green stream.

Figure S.5. Aspen Plus flowsheet of the coating and final treatment stage, including coating application, drying, vapor separation, and cooling of the final product.

S.1.6 Biological Treatment

As illustrated in Figure S.6, the biological treatment stage begins with the conditioning of the incoming wastewater stream, followed by the addition of nutrients required for microbial activity. Blue streams represent water flows, while purple streams indicate the addition of chemical nutrients. The anaerobic and aerobic reactors are shown sequentially, where the organic load is reduced through biological conversion processes. Air supply to the aerobic reactor is represented by yellow stream. Gas generation and removal are highlighted through the grey vertical gas streams, representing the formation and separation of biogas and vent gases during treatment. The resulting treated liquid stream continues toward the subsequent stages of the wastewater treatment system.

Figure S.6. Aspen Plus flowsheet of the biological treatment stage, including cooling, nutrient addition, anaerobic and aerobic reactors, and gas separation.

S.1.7 Flocculation, sedimentation and flotation

Figure S.7 depicts the final stages of the wastewater treatment system, where solids separation and effluent polishing take place. The addition of coagulants and polymers is indicated by the purple streams, facilitating particle aggregation prior to sedimentation. Blue streams correspond to the clarified liquid phase progressing through the system, while brown streams represent sludge flows removed during sedimentation and flotation and directed toward sludge handling units. Air input to the flotation system is represented by yellow streams, highlighting the generation of air-saturated water used for bubble formation. The flotation section enables the separation of remaining suspended

solids through bubble attachment and its rise to the surface. The treated effluent is shown as a dark-blue stream exiting the system, which is the final water stream that can either be discharged or reused within the process. In the reuse configuration considered in this study, this stream is recirculated and mixed with process water upstream of the pulping stage, contributing to the reduction of freshwater demand.

Figure S.7. Aspen Plus flowsheet of the flocculation, sedimentation, and flotation stages, including sludge handling and treated effluent streams.

S.2. Model Assumptions and Simplifications

Table 1. Key assumptions and simplifications adopted in the Aspen Plus model for the representation of the paperboard production system.

No.	Category	Assumption
1	Operation	Model assumes steady state operation
2	Energy scope	Electrical and mechanical loads of auxiliary equipment (e.g. pumps, vacuum systems, fans, drives) are excluded
3	Reject handling (energy)	No energy consumption is included for the reject separation and dewatering stages
4	Reject handling (material)	Reject streams are assumed to exit the system after the reject press; Incineration of rejects is considered a downstream treatment process and excluded from system boundary
5	Sludge handling	Sludge cake from wastewater treatment is assumed to exit the system after the centrifuge, with no further treatment modelled
6	Press section	Mechanical dewatering energy in the press section is not included
7	Steam system	Only low-pressure (LP) steam is produced by the boiler and supplied to the board machine
8	Dryer	Dryer modelled as single lumped unit without representing individual cylinders
9	Heat recovery	Heat recovery is represented via flash steam reuse and indirect heating of process stream; dedicated recovery units (e.g. scrubbers, ventilation systems) are not modelled.
10	Cooling system	Cooling water systems are not explicitly modelled; recoverable heat is assumed reused or neglected
11	Water system	Wire-pit temperature approximated by mixed whitewater from forming and pressing sections
11	Process detail	Minor recycle loops and control systems are not included

S.3. ISO 59020:2024 indicators: Water Intensity and Energy Intensity

Table 2 below presents the two circular economy (CE) indicators, namely *water intensity* and *energy intensity*, as defined in ISO 59020:2024 [2]. For these indicators, the table includes its reference code, the broader category to which they belong, a brief description and the general calculation formula. The table includes the ISO classification of each indicator (mandatory, optional, or additional). The accompanying comments provide context on the relevance of each indicator to the system under study and highlight any limitations or assumptions affecting its evaluation.

Table 2 : ISO 59020:2024 [2] indicators relevant for process-level application

Indicators	ISO classification	Definitions	Indicator Category	Formula	Comments
B4.3 Energy Intensity	Additional	The amount of total energy used to produce a given amount of output or activity.	Energy	$EI = \frac{E_{in,total}}{M_{product}}$ <i>[MJ/kg product]</i>	Total energy consumption depends on system-wide mass and energy interactions and cannot be determined from isolated unit data. A consistent evaluation requires integrated mass and energy balances across the process, making process simulation necessary.
B.5.3 Water intensity	Additional	Water used per unit of output, calculated as total water withdrawal or consumption divided by product output (mass or unit)	Water	$WI = \frac{V_{in,total}}{M_{product}}$ <i>[m³/kg product]</i>	Requires determination of total system water use, which depends on internal recirculation and process interactions. Process simulation is required to resolve system-wide water balances and evaluate the indicator.

S.4. Circularity Indicator Results Across Operating Scenarios

Table 3 below presents variation of the two circularity indicators Water Intensity (WI) and Energy Intensity (EI) as a function of freshwater temperature and reuse rate. These results complement the results presented in Figure 3 in the article.

Table 3. Summary of water intensity and energy intensity results across freshwater temperature and water reuse variations

Temperature (°C)	Reuse rate (%)	WI (m ³ /t)	EI (kWh/t)
5	0	14.95	1635.53
5	10	13.65	1591.62
5	20	12.30	1552.62
5	30	11.27	1530.02
5	40	9.96	1492.71
5	50	8.76	1461.25
5	60	7.60	1432.56
10	0	14.73	1563.45
10	10	13.57	1542.59
10	20	12.41	1512.37
10	30	11.19	1457.74
10	40	10.01	1462.64
10	50	8.72	1432.11
10	60	7.63	1412.70
15	0	14.69	1501.41
15	10	13.54	1477.80
15	20	12.33	1458.49
15	30	11.12	1431.90
15	40	9.94	1414.38
15	50	8.83	1394.82
15	60	7.61	1374.11
20	0	14.52	1441.30
20	10	13.60	1428.01
20	20	12.43	1414.49
20	30	11.21	1400.24
20	40	10.01	1386.08
20	50	8.75	1368.89
20	60	7.65	1360.80

References

- [1] Aspen Technology, Inc. (n.d.). *Aspen Plus® (process simulation software)*
<https://www.aspentech.com/en/products/engineering/aspentech-plus>
- [2] International Organization for Standardization. (2024b). *ISO 59020:2024 - Circular economy — Measuring and assessing circularity performance.*

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